

D2.1 Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation plan

Work Package:	WP2
Deliverable:	D2.1
Due date:	February 2021
Submission date:	10 th February 2021
Responsible Partner:	Ersilia Foundation
Version:	Final
Author:	Maria Teresa Guevara
Deliverable Type:	R
Dissemination Level:	PU

Contents

Introduction	3
1 Content and main principles	4
1.1 Project Summary	4
1.2 Main project results and dissemination contents	4
1.3 Main communication and dissemination principles	7
2 Target Audience	8
3 Main dissemination and communication activities	9
3.1 Visual identity	9
3.2 Website (New Mobility Cultures & Policies Hub)	10
3.3 New Mobility Cultures & Policies Journal	10
3.4 Social Media Networks	10
3.5 Webinars, Workshops & Other activities	11
3.6 Other project dissemination initiatives	12
3.7 Final communication and dissemination report	12
4 Targeted communication campaigns	12
4.1 Targeted Communication Campaign 1	12
4.2 Targeted Communication Campaign 2	13
4.3 Targeted Communication Campaign 3	14

INTRODUCTION

Communication and Dissemination plan is a strategy of making the results and deliverables of a project available to the project target groups, stakeholders and to the wider audience. Communication and Dissemination plan is essential for take-up, and is crucial for the success of the project and for the sustainability of outputs in the long term.

The purpose of REBALANCE Communication and Dissemination plan is to:

- Promote – to ‘disseminate’ REBALANCE outputs and results;
- Raise awareness – to bring the attention on the project theme;
- Engage – get input/feedback from the community;
- Make sustainable – ensure that the effects will be sustained after the project.

Communication and Dissemination plan is a part of the overall project REBALANCE implementation plan. The Communication and Dissemination plan explains how the visibility of the project outputs and outcomes will be maximized, and how the project outcomes will be shared with project target groups, stakeholders, relevant institutions, organisations, and individuals. Communication and Dissemination plan is developed in consultation with the project partners and explains:

- Content and main principles;
- Target audience;
- Main dissemination activities;
- Targeted communication campaigns;
- Collaboration principles, responsibilities and timing;
- Monitoring progress on reaching key performance Indicators;
- Dissemination reporting.

Approval by:

- ISSINOVA, Italy
- Dresden University of Technology, Germany
- Gustave Eiffel University, France
- University of Žilina, Slovakia
- Osborne Clarke, Belgium
- Ersilia Foundation, Spain

1 CONTENT AND MAIN PRINCIPLES

1.1 Project Summary

As a cultural and political initiative, the REBALANCE overall aim is to conduct an open deliberative forward-looking exercise towards a transformative transport policy strategy in favour of a paradigm shift in mobility, pushing for the more effective adoption of cultural and social values not yet fully considered, better aligned with the SDGs and the mounting concerns about climate change. The critical review of the present also in the light of the recent COV19 pandemic which drastically affected our lifestyles, the vision over the future and the roadmap to achieve it, will be embedded in a Manifesto with the aim to stimulate European policymakers to adopt concrete legal and political measures while moving the wider European communities towards a radical change.

While pursuing the overall strategic objectives as listed above, REBALANCE is expected to contribute to the EC overall objectives for mobility and transport according to the four principles pointed out by the European Commissioner Adina-Ioana Vălean in her speech of January 2020 on 'EU strategy for mobility and transport: Measures needed by 2030 and beyond' :

- Making the transport system as whole more sustainable;
- Making sustainable alternative solutions available to EU citizens and businesses;
- Respecting the polluter-pays principle in all transport modes;
- Fostering connectivity and access to transport for all.

In addition, REBALANCE will contribute to the implementation of the European Green Deal - and the United Nation's 2030 Agenda and the SDGs- by turning the climate and environmental challenges into opportunities for a transition to a more sustainable and inclusive mobility paradigm protecting the health and well-being of all citizens.

REBALANCE is finally expected to contribute to the realisation of the Europe 2020 objectives for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth by stimulating mobility providers with insights and hints to meet the demand for a new mobility culture. In so doing, the project will help strengthen education, reduce social exclusion and generate jobs across Europe.

1.2 Main project results and dissemination contents

The main purpose of dissemination strategy is to ensure the visibility of the project results and increase the impact of the project on the target group. Below the list of the potential exploitable products or results; identifies the target groups that these products are aimed at; explains how these groups will benefit from using these products; and finally, specifies the dissemination channels and activities that we will use to reach our target groups and deliver these products to them.

Main project results are:

Exploitable products	Target groups	Benefits from take up REBALANCE products	Dissemination channels/activities
Online Journal Mobility Cultures and Policies in Europe	all	Opening up new ideas contributing to envision a new mobility paradigm shift	Published every four months (6 in total). The first issue will be devoted to exploring cultures and policies in the CV19 aftermath, and the last one to introduce the Manifesto it-self.
			Shared via social networks and New Mobility Cultures and Policies hub
			Open calls for papers will be regularly launched and a peer-review process will be carried out by REBALANCE partners
New Mobility Cultures and Policies Hub	all	A transdisciplinary knowledge-sharing space on mobility cultures and policies in Europe, involving thinkers, experts, stakeholders and policy decision-makers	Online platform
			Broadcast Live Interviews to visionary thinkers and high-level mobility experts, organising Q&A chats and opening discussion through social networks.
			Open consultations and online workshops address directly to target audiences
			Shared via social networks
Mobility Culture and Value Framework	1, 2	A critical analysis of Current Values embedded into personal preferences and mobility behaviour and behind the politics of mobility	Related activities: Generative dialogues on theoretical framework considering CV19 Lasting Impacts with mobility high-level experts- broadcast live and recorded in hub
			Mobility Values Focus group to carry out a values assessment represented in current narrative, involving relevant experts and stakeholders, event hosted in hub.
			Deliverables will be shared via the New Mobility Cultures and Policies hub and social networks
Critical analysis on current travel patterns and emerging mobility values	1, 2	Summarizes the analysis of the state-of-the-art on the definition of European-wide Mobility Values, traveller's value proposition of mobility across different transport modes.	This deliverable will be shared via the New Mobility Cultures and Policies hub and social networks
Analysis of the role of communication in shaping European mobility culture	all	In-depth analyse on the different forms of media, social media and institutional communication and the way mobility values are channelled to citizens. review of advertisements, movies, press will be carried out... etc	This deliverable will be shared via the New Mobility Cultures and Policies hub and social networks
			Related Multimedia resources will be part of the hub dedicated section on mobility and transport communication strategies
Trends and drivers shaping the future of European transport	all	Identification of present trends, drivers, wild cards and weak signals unveiling and characterizing the philosophical and	Related activities: Explorative conversations with high-level experts on the Mobility of the Future
			This deliverable will be shared via the New Mobility Cultures and Policies hub and social networks

		cultural backdrop against which mobility culture is shaped	Related Multimedia resources will be part of the hub dedicated section on mobility cultures trends and drivers
Transport vision at 2050 based on alternative narrative	all	Identification, and in-depth characterisation of an alternative narrative that better combines the most desirable features in terms of long-term sustainability, with the most faithful reflection of the profound societal values needs and aspirations and of their possible future dynamics.	<p>Related activities: Online focus group Imagining Future Scenarios on Mobility Cultures Focus Group to implement a forward-looking exercise- with experts and stakeholders, hosted online in the hub.</p> <p>Face to face Scenario workshop: Imagining the Ideal Future Scenario based on the scenarios space and alternative narratives identified</p> <p>Deliverables will be shared via the New Mobility Cultures and Policies hub and social networks</p>
Transport strategy towards a paradigm shift in mobility and related Roadmap and Policy Guide	1, 2	The REBALANCE proposed policy strategy and the associated roadmap are inputs that can be directly used by relevant stakeholders for setting up alternative policies regarding mobility	<p>A Delphi-survey will be conducted followed by a Consensus online workshop with EU experts on public law</p> <p>This deliverable will be shared via the New Mobility Cultures and Policies hub and social networks</p>
New concepts for regulatory policies	1,2	The REBALANCE proposal of a manifesto and the redefinition of the “public interest” indicates a series of orientations to reshape the European societal regulatory instruments	This deliverable will be shared via the New Mobility Cultures and Policies hub and social networks
Guidance for infrastructure and investment policies	1,2	REBALANCE will provide guidance on needed evolutions to the assessment methods (CBA, etc.) in order to promote alternative mobility values	This deliverable will be shared via the New Mobility Cultures and Policies hub and social networks
Manifesto for a New Mobility Culture	all	Stimulate European policymakers to adopt concrete legal and political measures while moving the wider European communities towards a radical change.	This deliverable will be shared via the New Mobility Cultures and Policies hub, social networks and in REBALANCE final event

1.3 Main communication and dissemination principles

1.3.1 PROJECT COMMUNICATION TEAM (PCT)

To foster the exchange on communication and dissemination, a Project Communication Team (PCT) is established to coordinate outreach activities and to exchange on dissemination and communication activities.

Partner Number	Organisation	PCT Members	Contacts
P1	ISINNOVA	Silvia Gaggi	sgaggi@isinnova.org
P2	ERSILIA	Marite Guevara	mguevara@ersilia.org
P3	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT DRESDEN	Lisa-Marie Schaefer	lisa-marie.schaefer@tu-dresden.de
P4	UNIVERSITE GUSTAVE EIFFEL	Alain Lhostis	alain.lhostis@univ-eiffel.fr
P5	ZILINSKA UNIVERZITA V ZILINE	GhadirPourhashem	Ghadir.Pourhashem@uniza.sk
P6	OSBORNE CLARKE	Cecilia Sbrolli	cecilia.sbrolli@osborneclarke.com

Local communication activities will target universities, research institutions, local business associations, city and regional authorities, and other entities deemed influential or valuable for local awareness-raising.

WP leaders will be aided in the creation of targeted social media initiatives for outreach to the local community (see social media initiatives below). The PCT will meet virtually on a monthly basis so WP2 leader can report on the progress of local initiatives.

1.3.2 VISUAL REBALANCE PROJECT PRESENCE

All project results, communication and dissemination material is obliged to display:

1. REBALANCE logo
2. Project number: No. 101007019
3. The EU flag and acknowledge the support received

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the grant agreement No. 101007019

2 TARGET AUDIENCE

The five target groups are:

1. Research community- (e.g. Universities, research institutes, company based product research) - The ambition of REBALANCE is to open up new avenues of thinking and research on the mobility issue; influencing the development of new policies, products, systems and services at the beginning of their life-cycle. The environment for mobility related research in Europe is very fragmented, with many uncoordinated parallel activities in different member states. At the European level, as part of the research framework programmes, there are research and innovation actions funded by the European Commission which provide useful channels for bringing together different initiatives and creating added value.
2. Policy makers and planners- At the level of national and trans-European networks (TENs), Governments, financial donor agencies and increasingly the private sector (within public/private partnerships) are the primary stakeholders. Stakeholders in urban and regional planning in formal planning frameworks linked to national funding, including Sustainable Urban Mobility Planning (SUMP) frameworks.
3. Mobility operators (e.g. on all major modes, car sharing companies etc.) These stakeholders will become more diverse and innovative, responding to public demand; using novel business models and harnessing the advantages of new ICT. Major stakeholders in this category are the airlines, rail companies, urban public transport operators and, to a lesser extent, coastal ferry companies and regional inland waterway services.
4. Mobility suppliers including ITS and virtual (e.g. aircraft, vehicle and vessel manufacturers, infrastructure, components, ITS systems, ticketing and booking systems etc.) This category of stakeholder is from the private sector, comprising multi-national companies working on a world market, and innovative SMEs promoting single mobility products. These sectors need to know people's changing lifestyles will affect the types of products they can put on the market.
5. Mobility related user groups and society at large (i.e. with a mission: by different modes and social group concerns as. European Cyclists Federation, European Trade Union Confederation, European Passengers' Federation, UITP). These represent a large group of private organisations at national and European

levels. They are not decision-makers but have mission statements that promote the use of particular modes of transport, or to protect the interests of particular social groups. They raise awareness among their membership, citizens at large, but particularly at the political level. In the first category, we can cite stakeholders like the European Cyclists Federation, Walk 21. In the second category, we can cite organisations such as HREA.

3 MAIN DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

In this part of document Dissemination and Communication channels and activities are defined, and the basis for all further outreach activities of this work package will be formed. The main objective of this part is to present how the Project intends to communicate and disseminate its purpose and outcomes, to facilitate take-up and transferability opportunities by interested parties. It provides practical guidance on how to do the project's communication work to most effectively achieve the project's objectives. It includes visual identity guidelines and will define the project's communication channels – social media, newsletters, and other efforts that will be used to disseminate the guidelines, framework and videos, thus raising awareness of the project and encouraging uptake and replication.

3.1 Visual identity

rebalance

This unique REBALANCE visual identity consists of an easily recognizable logo. The main idea behind the logo is to be disruptive and to emphasize the humanistic dimension as a priority. The two circles inscribed in the infinity shape make a reference to the characteristic structural element of the contemporary transport means, the wheels.

Moreover, the reference to the lemniscate (ribbons) expressed by the infinity shape, refers to the two speed worlds, the equilibrium and the resilience of the new mobility cultural values which the project conveys. In today's world where the current mobility culture has led to unsustainable patterns, in social and environmental terms, the infinity symbolism is used metaphorically with respect to the limitless opportunities that the paradigm shift in mobility aims to bring by integrating emerging social values which are intangible and cannot be measured.

Reference: Euler's infinity sign

An integral part of this document is a REBALANCE logo Brand book which aims to present a logo and communicate the appropriate use of it.

Templates of Word, PowerPoint are developed to provide a professional and unique look for REBALANCE project internal and external documentation and presentation.

3.2 Website (New Mobility Cultures & Policies Hub)

The website address (URL): <https://rebalancemobility.eu/>

Ersilia Foundation produce a project website which will act as the first point of contact for many stakeholders and provide a portal to the project outputs and outcomes.

Main website features are foreseen:

The website will contain all information regarding project aim and progress, current status of activities, news, dissemination and instructions to take part in the project activities. Short introductions and contact details for all members of the consortium will also be available.

The number of visitors, downloads, website hits will be tracked by web traffic analysis tools, allowing the consortium to overview how well the website reaches both target groups and stakeholders.

The site will be accessible via apps on a mobile phone, on iPad or any tablet devices and on desktop devices.

The website will have links with Social media channels: LinkedIn and Twitter.

The website will be constantly updated and consequently it will be a dynamic and up-to-date source of information for target groups and stakeholders.

The website will be maintained for at least two years after the project ends.

3.3 New Mobility Cultures & Policies Journal

The journal will be published every four months (6 in total). The first issue will be devoted to exploring cultures and policies in the CV19 aftermath, and the last one to introduce the Manifesto it-self. The Editorial Board will be composed by REBALANCE partners and external experts.

Ersilia Foundation will develop the journal template and all partners will contribute to newsletters development and provide a list of contacts among the stakeholder groups that might be interested in receiving information about the project.

REBALANCE contact database and mailing lists will be created from the early stage of the project and will be constantly updated. It will be used for direct communication during the project lifetime. It is foreseen that all partners will involve national and international representatives to REBALANCE contact database of more than 1500 subscribers, interested in a paradigm shift in mobility and transport policies.

3.4 Social Media Networks

Social Media Networks. ISINNOVA partner will run social media accounts linked to the project in order to promote the results to a wider, international audience online. During the preparation phase, partners have analyzed and chosen most appropriate channels, including:

1. Twitter account: <https://twitter.com/RebalanceEu>

ISINNOVA will be responsible for overall Twitter administration and monitoring.

Each partner will take responsibility for maintaining according to the established plan: share links or articles with ISINNOVA PCT representative and connect and disseminate page to their circles.

2. LinkedIn account: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/rebalance-eu-b95340205/>

ISINNOVA will be responsible for overall LinkedIn page administration and monitoring.

Each partner will take responsibility for maintaining according to the established plan: share links or articles with ISINNOVA PCT representative and connect and disseminate page to their circles.

3.5 Webinars, Workshops & Other activities

Partnership consortium possess the opinion that the best advertisement is demonstrating a working product. Partners will plan each webinar, focus group workshop and final conference early in advance, matching with a significant stage in the project which they particularly wish to disseminate, or to help recruit for the training being provided through REBALANCE. It is foreseen ten different types of activities:

1. In-depth talks with thinkers- realising 10 public webinars (lead: WP2)
2. Generative dialogues on theoretical framework- having 10 public interviews (lead: WP3)
3. Mobility values focus groups (lead: WP3)
4. Explorative conversations on the mobility of the future (lead: WP4)
5. Imagining future scenarios on mobility cultures- Focus group (lead: WP4)
6. Open consultation on the vision (lead: WP4)
7. Public interest definition focus group (lead: WP5)
8. Design a roadmap and outline feasible strategies- Back-casting exercise involving experts and stakeholders (lead: WP5)
9. Co-creative development of a Manifesto for a new European mobility culture and policy. (lead:WP2)
10. Final conference to showcase the results of the project, and to discuss outcomes and further exploitation

The final number of participants in each webinar, focus group workshop and final conference will allow measuring how many people have been introduced to the project. It is foreseen that REBALANCE webinars and workshops will be disseminated through

European websites that displays research and innovation-related conferences and events. The contacts with various networks in the field will be made to share our experience and get insights from colleagues.

3.6 Other project dissemination initiatives

Partners will commit to undertaking additional local dissemination initiatives within their own areas, such as presenting project in any other possible international conferences and exhibitions. Aside from presenting the project's work at relevant scientific and stakeholder events all consortium partners will help raise awareness of the project at the national, regional and local level by encouraging policy makers, local and regional authorities, researchers, public transport operators, providers of mobility products and services, and user group associations to adopt the project's Manifesto. The project presentations will be made in project partners' countries or abroad, adjusting the PowerPoint slides template, developed by Ersilia Foundation team.

3.7 Final communication and dissemination report

At the end of the project, a communication and dissemination report will be produced. This report will be an overview of the most successful dissemination activities, but it will also comprise an analysis of the efficiency of the dissemination activities during the project. Based on this assessment, a set of recommendations will be produced that will provide a good base for the elaboration of a strategy for the sustainable and transformative transport policy of the future.

4 TARGETED COMMUNICATION CAMPAIGNS

REBALANCE approach and ambition will generate an interest from different target groups already mentioned. Key representatives from each target group will be contacted from early days of the project in order to understand the characteristics of the group and the best ways to communicate with them.

The partners will play an active role in representing REBALANCE and its results at conferences and seminars at the international and European level, will mention it in interactive e-mailing lists, will seek to publish information about the REBALANCE experience and approach in journals and other publications, and will 'piggy-back' on opportunities arising through involvement in other initiatives.

3 targeted communication campaigns with European and global outreach are planned focusing on specific stage in the project which they particularly wish to disseminate, or to help recruit for the webinars and workshops being provided through REBALANCE.

4.1 Targeted Communication Campaign 1

Period: December 2020 – April, 2021

Focus: Dissemination for Awareness

Main aim - introduce the project, the consortium, objectives, potential outcomes, benefits for target group.

CC1 Activities:

- Create REBALANCE Logo, templates, develop Brand book
- Develop REBALANCE Communication and Dissemination Plan
- Develop REBALANCE Intro Presentation
- Launch a Website- New Mobility Cultures & Policies Hub
- Launch 2 social media channels
- Launch the first Online Journal Mobility Cultures and Policies in Europe
- Launch 10 REBALANCE talks- In-depth online interviews with thinkers
- Launch 10 generative dialogues on REBALANCE theoretical framework
- Develop the first draft Manifesto for a new mobility culture including a Roadmap towards a transport paradigm shift- to start with the end in mind.
- Develop, and spread Newsletter No.1 and No.2 to disseminate webinars with Thinkers
- Launch Social media channels
- Publish information about REBALANCE in partner websites

CC1 Results:

- Number of website visitors: >1000
- Project presentation in National, international events/meetings: >2
- Newsletter of subscribers: >40 subscribers
- Number of followers in social media networks: > 50
- REBALANCE references in websites: >5
- CC1 Activity template and partners responsibilities: Annex No.1

4.2 Targeted Communication Campaign 2

Period: May, 2021 – July, 2022

Focus: Invitation of different stakeholders, experts and thinkers to take part in the REBALANCE deliberation and co-creation activities reflecting the forward-looking exercise embedded in the project's workplan. Additionally, the dissemination at this stage is also focused on collecting contacts of stakeholder groups for the empirical research and to address interested users to maximise future outreach.

Main aim: Establish a generative dialogue with visionary thinkers, mobility experts and stakeholders through the Mobility Cultures & Policies Hub; Increase project's visibility and effectiveness by finding and building on synergies with other initiatives and projects working on mobility and transport issues as well as changes in cultural values in a broader sense; Progressively disseminate project's results as achieved by the consortium in a continuous co-creation exercise with the REBALANCE community.

CC2 Activities:

- Organise online event in M6: *Mobility Values Focus group* to carry out a values assessment represented in current narrative (Audience: Restricted to invited experts and stakeholders)
- Organise online event in M7-9: *Explorative conversations on the Mobility of the Future* between thinkers and high-level experts in order to identify present trends (Audience: Open to any interested person or institution)
- Organise online event in M10-12: *Imagining Future Scenarios on Mobility Cultures Focus Group* to implement a forward-looking exercise (Audience: Restricted to stakeholders and other experts to be invited)
- Organise 2 days face to face event in M12-14: *Imagining the Ideal Future Scenario* (Audience: Restricted to stakeholders and other experts to be invited)
- Launch Open Consultation on the Vision in M12-14
- Organise Public Interest Definition Focus Group in M17-19
- Launch the 2nd, 3rd and 4th Online Issue of the Journal on Mobility Cultures and Policies in Europe-
- Prepare website news and updates on New Mobility Cultures & Policies Hub
- Develop, and spread Newsletter No.3,4,5 and 6
- Publish news and invite participants on Social media channels
- Publish information about REBALANCE in partner websites
- Present project in National, international events/meetings
- Publish Press releases
- Publish information REBALANCE in other websites

CC2 Results:

- Number of unique visitors to the project website: 4000
- Project presentation in National, international events/meetings: 6
- Number of subscribers to the newsletter: 150 subscribers
- Number of followers in social media networks – 300
- REBALANCE references in websites – 18

4.3 Targeted Communication Campaign 3

Period: August, 2022 – December, 2022

Focus: The final stage of the REBALANCE project is dedicated to disseminating the results and accomplishments. The outcomes of the project will be widely disseminated

to the scientific community and within various policy fields as well as to a wider public and the EU citizens at large.

Main aim – ultimately ensure a wider uptake of project’s results thereby enabling our target groups to commit to and exploit the REBALANCE’s “New Mobility Cultures & Policies Hub”, the “Online Journal on Mobility Cultures and Policies in Europe” and the ‘Manifesto for a new mobility culture including a Roadmap towards a transport paradigm shift’.

CC3 Activities:

- Organize Roadmap Workshop- back-casting exercise in M20
- Present project in National, international events/meetings
- Prepare website news and updates
- Develop, and spread Newsletter No.3
- Publish news and invite participants on Social media channels
- Publish information about REBALANCE in partner websites
- Publish Press releases, 1 scientific publication in peer-review journal
- Publish information REBALANCE in other websites

CC3 Results:

- Number of website visitors: >4000
- Project presentation in National, international events/meetings: >6
- Newsletter of subscribers: >150 subscribers
- Number of followers in social media networks: > 300
- REBALANCE references in websites: >18
- Press releases delivered to traditional media, TV and Radio interview: 1
- Manifesto: 1

Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for the content of this document lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein

